
Sustainability of Women Employment Generation in Rural Area due to Government Scheme

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Abstract:

India's economy is the fastest growing economy in the world. India is known as the land of villages. Even today, 70 per cent of India's population lives in rural areas. The people here are dependent on agriculture and agriculture is dependent on the vagaries of nature.

People in rural areas have to deal with a lot of problems. For example, agriculture is dependent on nature, low wages, lack of jobs, malnutrition, poverty, water, electricity, communication, transportation, health, migration, etc.

In rural areas, women also play a very important role equally with men. Women are 50% of the society, who work round the clock for the welfare of the human race, who wake up for the family, who give dedication without expecting any compensation. The family institution is based on the sacrifice and labour of women. According to rural tradition, women's place was in the home. Now, however, things have changed. The reason is to empower rural women. It has become a necessity for the society to ensure sustainable development of the country. It has also become necessary for rural women to get an education and make their place in various fields. For this, the government is also implementing several schemes by introducing several bills and policies.

Introduction:

Many scholars and social reformers seem to have come up with a plan to bring the women section of the society out of the stereotypes and caste system. But this class is yet to gain independence. Sane Guruji, in his book "Indian Women's Life", has said that society needs women's intelligence, but it is also in the interest of women to be self-sufficient. So it's time for them to insist that they take responsibility for independence.

Indian culture is an agrarian culture and rural women have contributed significantly to the progress of the agricultural sector. About 70% of the Indian economy is related to agriculture and agro-related industries. Of course, rural area have the highest number of women. Also, the invisible work of these women is most

visible. If the value of their invisible nature's work is extracted, it will certainly add to the national income. Most of the country's natural resources are found in rural areas. Therefore, agricultural development in rural areas is the most important and primary source of income.

Therefore, we cannot underestimate the importance of agriculture. That is why the contribution of the agriculture sector to India's GDP growth is remarkable. About 80 per cent of women in rural areas are engaged in agriculture, and we see many small, cottage industries related to agriculture in the rural areas. Women contribute to agriculture through many roles such as farmers, entrepreneurs, and workers. Rural women are building the nation by contributing their work as a responsible

citizen in various ways such as poultry farming, animal husbandry, goat, sheep farming, occupation dairy farming, horticulture, horticulture, plantation, forestry fishing, planting to post-harvest work, mowing, production of papad and pickles, summer work, raw materials required for the production of finished goods, sewing, restaurant, tourism and entertainment.

They are becoming sources of other industries and contributing to others by generating income for themselves.

Research Objectives:

1. Understand the concept of women empowerment.
2. Review central and state government schemes for women empowerment.
3. To study the welfare approach of the government on the basis of various schemes implemented for women.
4. To understand the role played by the Government Scheme in living standards, generating self-employment and employment opportunities in rural area.

Research assumptions:

1. Government schemes were implemented effectively.
2. Gender inequality.

Research Methods:

The second material is supported for the present research paper. It uses published books, magazines, weekly magazines, various newspapers, brochures on various schemes of the government, internet.

Limitations of Research:

Since the scope of central and state government schemes is very broad, the study of schemes implemented only for women has been limited.

The Constitution gives rights to women. The information doesn't seem to have reached them as much as they should. The Maharashtra government announced the first women's policy in 1994. It was changed

over time to set a second women's policy in 2001 and a third in 2014. All these policies mainly consider violence against women, women's laws, economic status reform, role of media, participation of NGOs, determination of schemes with women at the center, development of self-help groups, Mudra yojana.

Job creation and improving employment capacity are the priorities of the government. Accordingly, the Government of India has taken various steps to create jobs in the country. Various long-term schemes/programmes/policies are included to make the country self-reliant and create employment opportunities as well as self-employment.

Review of Literature:

1. **Solunkhe, G. J. (2016)** noticed that the PMEGP schemes is helpful to those who are unemployed and wants some financial help to take the existing business opportunity. This scheme is helpful to those peoples who believe in self help and help to others by increasing employment opportunity. This scheme is helps to improve the hidden skill of entrepreneurship in rural peoples and to make self sufficient. Increase in the income level of rural people increase the national income of country too.
2. **Bagul, S.A. (2017)** noted that India is a developing country, which makes it very essential for government to promote entrepreneurship more. Government today was providing lot of useful schemes for women as well, but the benefits are far beyond reach due to rural educational exposure. Country needs to focus on job giving youth rather them job seeking youth. All we need to do today is instill a feeling of entrepreneurship in the youth today.
3. **Motik, S. (2000)** also tried to connecting women entrepreneur and economic growth and found that women

entrepreneurs help in economic development by job creating, increase saving that results energize in working capital, increase business volume.

4. **Priyanaka Sharma (2013)** highlighted the development ways for women entrepreneurship. These are providing better educational facilities, adequate training programs, vocational training, and establishing special target groups for women entrepreneurs etc. This study also highlighted the problems faced by women entrepreneurs. These are male dominating society, inadequate financial assistance, women family obligations etc.
5. **Devi Rama T. (2017)** researched and give recommendations as women constitute one-half of India's population, without their engagement and empowerment, rapid economic progress is not possible, for sustainable development women empowerment is of utmost value. along with government, civil society organizations and allother stake holders must come forward and involve in the women empowerment process it is the need of hour.

Various schemes of the government for Women:

1) Training and Employment Assistance Program :

The Government of India launched the Women Training and Employment Assistance Programme Scheme in 1986-87. The objective of this scheme is to develop poor, promising, rural and urban women. Agriculture, animal husbandry, dairying, horticulture, fisheries, handloom, handicrafts, sewing arts, khadi and village industries, silk industry, etc. have been covered in this program. It is being implemented by public sector organisations, state corporations, District Rural Development Authority, cooperative societies, federations and registered NGOs that have been in existence for at least three

years.

The objective is to develop truly poor rural and urban women and provide them with funds through the central government and implementing agencies. The scheme is for labourers, unpaid, daily wage labourers, migrants, women-led families, tribal and disadvantaged groups.

Under this scheme, work is done to improve the skills of needy women so that they can get employment or start their own employment. Through this, women are involved and trained in various fields like agriculture, horticulture, dairy, handloom, sewing and fisheries.

2) Swayamsiddha Yojana:

On July 12, 2001, the central government changed the name of Indira Gandhi Mahila Yojana to Swayamsiddha Yojana. It is an integrated scheme for the development and empowerment of women. The main objective of this scheme is to ensure the social, economic and all-round development of women. At the same time, the aim is to create awareness about economic issues.

3) Balika Samriddhi Yojana:

The scheme was launched by the Government of India on October 2, 1997, under the Women and Child Development Policy for the convenience of girls. This important initiative is being implemented to welcome the birth of girls in the society as well as to increase the quality of education. At the same time, the objective of the scheme is to support girls and motivate them to take up various activities that generate income for their own well-being.

Banks and financial institutions are unable to lend to rural women as they do not have enough money and lack education. If women get the right education and inheritance rights, they can definitely progress.

4) Udyogini Scheme :

This scheme is a very important scheme for women empowerment. This

scheme is for women already started or are going to do an industry. Under this scheme, a loan of Rs 3 lakh is given to women between the ages of 18 years and 45 years to widows, destitute or disabled women belonging to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes to work in the business, agriculture, retail and small enterprise sectors.

5) Business loans of Bharatiya Mahila Bank:

Bharatiya Mahila Bank provides business loans to women entrepreneurs who want to start new ventures in retail and SME sectors. Loans up to a maximum of `1 lakh are given to women entrepreneurs. The business loan scheme also offers a discount of `20 crore and 0.25%.

6) Annapurna Yojana:

This scheme is a special loan scheme of State Bank of India. Under this scheme, loan facility is provided to women. Loans up to `50,000 are given for pot cutlery, gas connection, refrigerator, mixer, grinder, hot case pot stand, tiffin box, working table, water filter etc. For this, the property of the business has to be kept as collateral with the guarantor. Women can repay this loan in 36 monthly installments.

7) Dena Shakti Yojana :

Dena Bank has launched a special Dena Shakti scheme for women to make women self-reliant and self-reliant. Under this scheme, loans up to `20 lakh are made available at a very low interest rate. This allows women to start their own businesses. Women get an interest subvention of 0.25% on loans received through this scheme and the repayment period is up to 10 years. The facility is also available for agricultural production, retailers and micro enterprises.

8) Cent Kalyan Yojana:

This is a loan scheme of the Central Bank of India. Loans up to `1 crore are provided through this scheme for micro and small scale industries. Overall, the scheme aims to finance women's business dreams.

9) Women's Initiative Fund Scheme:

Punjab National Bank launched the Mahila Udyog Nidhi Yojana for women to make women self-reliant and start businesses. Under this scheme, women can start their own business. At the same time, they can acquire new technologies and new skills. Under this scheme, loans up to `10 lakh can be availed for beauty parlours, cable TV networks, catering, hotels, nurseries, care centres, laundry, mobile repairs and have to be repaid over a period of 5 to 10 years.

10) Stree Shakti Package:

The scheme has been launched to provide financial assistance to poor and destitute women. The scheme provides loans through State Bank of India and other public sector banks. Loans range from `50,000 to `2 lakh for retail trade and business and `50,000 to `25 lakh for msme. Women get a 0.50% discount on interest rates. Under this scheme, no collateral is accepted up to a loan of `5 lakh.

11) Stand Up India Scheme:

On April 5, 2016, the stand-up India loan scheme was launched by the government to allow Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, Backward Classes and women to start their own businesses. Through this scheme, loans ranging from `1 lakh to `10 lakh are provided. The scheme can be availed from 18 years to 65 years. Under this scheme, the repayment period is up to 7 years.

12) Mudra Loan Scheme for Women:

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Loan Yojana is a business loan scheme. Under this scheme, unsecured loans up to `10 lakh are provided in three types.

- A) **Shishu Loan Scheme:** Loans up to 50,000 are provided under this scheme.
- B) **Kishore Loan Scheme:** Under this scheme, loans ranging from `50,000 to `5 lakh are provided to women.
- C) **Youth Loan Scheme:** These women are given loans ranging from `5 lakh to

₹10 lakh.

13) Orient Women's Development Scheme:

The scheme is implemented by Oriental Bank for women. Under the scheme, only women are included and they are given ownership rights of about 51% of the shares. Through this scheme, women get a 2% discount on interest rates. The scheme provides loans ranging from ₹10 lakh to ₹25 lakh for Small Scale Industries. No guarantor is required. Enterprising women can repay the loan over a period of 7 years.

14) Training plan for women:

The objective of the scheme is to provide vocational training to women above 15 years of age. It gives priority to destitute women and widows who have no support from anyone. They get whatever is fixed amount for this on a regular basis.

15) Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme:

On the eve of Independence Day 1993, the then Prime Minister in his speech said that the government was committed to launch the Pradhan Mantri Rojgar Yojana to provide employment opportunities to the youth. The scheme was formally launched on October 2, 1993, the birth anniversary of the Father of the Nation, Mahatma Gandhi. This scheme is implemented in each district through Directorate of Industries through District Industries Centre. In Mumbai and suburbs, the scheme is implemented through Assistant Director (Industries) Mumbai Metropolitan Area, Worli, Mumbai. Initially the scheme was implemented only in urban areas but from April 1994 it was also implemented in rural areas. This scheme has taken the place of employment scheme for boys and girls.

This scheme is a combination of Pradhan Mantri Rojgar Yojana (PMRY) and Rural Employment Generation Program (REGP). This scheme is implemented for unemployed youth in both rural and urban areas in coordination with Khadi and Village

Industries Commission and Khadi and Village Industries Board. KVIC routes government subsidy through designated banks for eventual disbursement to the beneficiaries / entrepreneurs directly into their bank accounts. The maximum cost of the project/unit admissible in manufacturing sector is ₹25 lakhs and in the business/service sector, it is ₹10 lakhs.

16) Seed Money Scheme:

The Government's Seed Capital Scheme (SMS) for educated unemployed has been implemented since 1976-77 through the Directorate of Industries and the Regional Development Corporation. Meanwhile, since 1983, the central government and banks have been implementing several schemes for financial assistance to entrepreneurs. As per Maharashtra's New Industrial Policy, 1983, the Seed Capital Assistance Scheme was merged with the Central Government's National Equity Fund Scheme as a few lakh people were found to be disadvantaged and the scheme was handed over to the District Industries Center for their implementation. From 1st October 1993, the Government of Maharashtra announced this scheme to provide employment to the educated unemployed.

Under this scheme self-employment activities are encouraged. Business/ service industries, with a project limit of ₹25 lakh are recommended for approval and the maximum loan limit is ₹3.75 and the bank gives 75 percent loan.

Under the scheme, local persons in the age group of 18 to 50 years with at least 7th Class passed and with the domicile of Maharashtra for at least 15 years are eligible to get the benefit of this scheme.

17) District Industry Centre Loan Scheme:

Micro and Small Enterprises are of great importance in India being an agriculture based nation. Micro and Small Enterprises require little capital and provide

ample employment opportunities. But currently micro and small scale industries are in crisis due to lack of capital, raw materials, effective management, trained manpower, electricity. To overcome all the problems, to increase the national income, and provide ample employment opportunities, the central and state governments have decided to set up various institutions for the development of such industries. District Industries Center Loan Scheme was started from 1978-79 to provide financial assistance to very small industries in semi-urban and rural areas to achieve their development and thereby create more employment opportunities and self-employment. This scheme is a district level scheme and is implemented at the district level through the District Industry Center Office. So that potential entrepreneurs can develop and get the facilities they need at one place.

There is no education or age requirement for this scheme. Also both the large industries and small scale industries should be eligible for registration.

Investment in machinery in the industry should be within 2 lakh. Bank provides 65 to 75 percent loans. The rate of interest is 4% and the seed capital loan can be repaid in 8 years.

Conclusion:

India is the youngest populous country in the world. More than 50 per cent of the working women of the population still do not have the status of entitlement and entitlement here. They have already been ignored. However, they make up more than 45% of the country's population. They are still not considered human resources in society. If these human resources are really used in the Indian economy and their participation in economic development increases, then surely the picture of the Indian economy will be even different. While the government is implementing

several schemes and policies for women empowerment, there is a need for an encouraging and safe environment for women's empowerment. Giving them the freedom to make decisions in a fear-free environment will reveal their immense potential.

However, today there are thousands of women entrepreneurs in the country whose ideals are before our eyes, which have been an inspiration for us.

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